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Development of Efficient, Sustainable and Environmental Friendly Cathode Material via Natural Fibre for the Energy Storage Application

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Abstract:

Herein, the present work reports on the development of efficient sustainable and environment friendly cotton fiber composite material by oxidative polymerization of aniline via in-site approach using MnO_2 as oxidating agent in acidic medium such as hydrochloric acid. The synthesized composite material was characterized by FTIR, FESEM and Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) investigation for their successful preparation and electrochemical performance for supercapacitor application. The presence of cyclic voltammogram, charge discharge cycle and lower charge transfer resistance of synthesized material shows good electrochemical behavior for supercapacitor application.

Introduction:

It is the prime necessities for scientific community and researcher to overcome the energy production and environmental pollution, petroleum based fuels must be replaced with the sustainable and renewable energy sources. Unutilized biomass and waste materials produced during energy production can be effectively utilized to synthesize carbon material for energy storage /conversion device such as battery, super capacitor, solar cells and fuel cells. This approach will be further resolve the difficulties related to safe recycling of waste ingredients and also the consumption of fossil fuel. In lieu of this we have synthesized natural fiber based composite material as suitable electrode which can be equipped for both supercapacitors and batteries applications. Supercapacitor are usually having high surface area and good electrical conductivity, which provide low resistivity and short in diffusion channel during electrochemical processing. The usage of fiber based composite material in energy storage devices provides both recycling of waste as well as ecofriendly materials for energy storage.

In the field of conducting polymers the synthesis of conducting fibers represents a fruitful technological area of research [1-6]. The recent surge of wearable and portable electronic equipment among the public has drawn the attention of the scientific community towards the novel development in this field [7]. The newly developed smart clothing is one of the examples in this prospect. For an example the newly developed smart clothing system which integrate wearable electronics with the everybody clothing system [8]. This type of innovative integrating system, system could be used in various fields such as sports and military equipment's which helping in monitoring as well as communicating with the potential when it needs [9]. The development of these types of system always associated with a lot of components such as sensors well-furnished communication system energy harvesting/energy storing devices, etc. Among this energy harvesting/energy storing device is the crucial part for the functioning of the smart garments [10]. The lighter weight with the excellent flexibility of the super capacitor has outburst the use of conventional power source such as battery solar power cells over it in such system embedding electrode material over the cotton fabric could help in developing such supercapacitor electrode which act excellently with retaining the properties of the fabric material [11]. This development could lead to a step towards the smart garments.

There are various reports citing towards the designing of such sustainable electrode for the supercapacitor application. Supercapacitor electrode from the natural fiber obtained from bamboo plant was developed by Zequine et al. [12]. Electrode material developed from jute fiber has shown the capacitance of 8.65 m F-cm^{-1} at current density 0.1 mA [13]. A report was obtained in which capacitor was made using cellulose nanofiber which could able to light up the LED light for 7 s after charging it will 18.7 v at 10 mA current for 10 s [14].

It has been explored the development of composite electrode material using natural/synthetic fibers with some metal oxide for supercapacitor application Gua at al. developed composite material MnO_2 graphene with synthetic fiber for flexible electrode for supercapacitor [15]. A composite of $\delta\text{-MnO}_2$ nano rods with soya pod carbon composite shows high charge storage capacity than that of pristine $\delta\text{-MnO}_2$. The develop material is found to retain 91% of the retention is capacitance even after 6000 discharging cycles[16].

An electrode material by the coating of TiO_2 nano particles over the cotton fiber was developed by Ozdemir et al. The TiO_2 decorated cotton fiber not only used as a PH sensor but it also shows excellent photo catalytic and anti microbial activity [17]. Previously it was reported that Ag-TiO_2 with cotton fibers synthesized by Araghez et al. Shows outstanding photo catalytic and anti bacterial activity [18]. Metal oxide fiber composite base electrode having explored for supercapacitor and sensor application. Metal oxide polymer fiber based electrode have rarely been studied.

Here, we have synthesized a low cost ecofriendly electrode material using conducting polymer metal oxide and fabric material used for clothing using the simple wet chemical method. The synthesized conducting polymer polyaniline metal oxide fabric material is subjected to electrochemical analysis which shows an excellent charge storage capacity and it can be used as supercapacitor application.

Material and method:

The aniline monomer was added to 1M HCL solution followed by the addition of metal oxide (MnO_2). The whole reaction mixture was then placed in an ice bath and the temperature of the reaction mixture was maintained at 0 to 5 degrees Celsius

for 30 minutes for initiation of polymerization. After the initiation of polymerization process the cotton fiber was added to it then it was stirred for few minutes and then it was left overnight. After the complete polymerization of aniline, the composite material of cotton fiber with polyaniline metal oxide was then placed in hot air at 70 degrees Celsius for drying this synthesized composite material. The PANI-MnO₂@CF electrode was subjected to FTIR for evaluating bonding parameter and FESEM for surface morphology and Cyclic Voltammetry (CV) investigation for redox behavior; galvanostatic and charging discharging behavior and finally impedance analysis to get information about charge transfer mechanism of PANI-MnO₂@CF electrode.

Result and Discussion:

Fig. 1: FTIR Spectra of PANI-MnO₂@CF

The peak obtained at 1496 and 1593 cm is due to c=c stretching vibration of the benzene and quinoid ring respectively [19]. The peak observed at 730 cm⁻¹ of the composite material is ascribed for Mn-O vibration [20]. The peak at 1238 cm⁻¹ is ascribed for the O-H bending vibration in the cotton fiber [21]. Along with this there is significant shift FT-IR peak corresponding to N=Q=N of PANI, C=O and β-glycosidic linkage of the cotton fabric to 1092 cm⁻¹, 1015 cm⁻¹, 863 cm⁻¹, indicate that there is strong interaction between the among the PANI@CF in the composite material [22]. The rest other peaks correspond to PANI as supported by previously report [23].

Surface Morphological Studies:

Fig. 2: FESEM image of PANI-MnO₂@CF composite material

The FESEM analysis shows that PANI has been successfully coated the over surface of the MnO₂ and cotton fiber. The wrapping of cotton fiber over the PANI@MnO₂ surface can be observed exhibiting inter connected structure. Such morphology with uniform distribution of PANI@MnO₂ with cotton fiber allows the effective diffusion and penetration of electrolyte ion within material for good electrochemical performance.

Electro Chemical Analysis of PANI-MnO₂@CF Electrode Material:

The CV of the synthesized PANI-MnO₂@CF was performed at different scan rate 5-100 mVs using three electrode system in which Ag/AgCl, Pt Electrode and sample were used as reference electrode, counter electrode and working electrode respectively in 1M aqueous KOH electrolyte solution. The CV analysis represents the redox behavior of the synthesized electrode material the potential window was set at -0.4 to 0.5 V. The spike in the voltammogram indicates that the electrode material undergoes redox reaction during the analysis process.

Fig. 3: Cyclic Voltammogram of PANI-MnO₂@CF composite material.

Fig. 4: Charging discharging (gcd) profile.

Fig. 5

Electrochemical impedance Nyquist plot from the figure 4 the charge discharge plot it is notable that the profile are nonlinear in nature. This non linearity could be ascribe to storage mechanism via Electric Double Layer Capacitance[EDLC] and pseudo capacitance via PANIMnO₂@CF. This signifies the typical formation of hybrid electrode material for supercapacitor application. The frequency behavior of synthesized material was carried out by Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy [EIS] analysis. The Fig. 4 and Fig. 5 shows that the electrode material we have synthesized is good for energy storage application.

Conclusion:

The synthesized MnO₂ decorated polyaniline stabilized by cotton fiber was successfully synthesized by in-situ chemical oxidative polymerization approach. This synthesized material can be used as electrode material for batteries supercapacitor application. Thus, the uses of fiber based composite material in energy storage devices provides both recycling of waste as well as ecofriendly materials for energy storage. And this could be the replacement of fossil fuel to some extent. In this way the climate change could be stopped without disturbing the environment.

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